

TOURISM ECONOMICS AND MANAGEMENT

Hayitboyeva Dilnoza

Student of UzMU

hayitboyeva03@gmail.com

97-120-66-61

Academic supervisor: UzMU teacher

Shahlo Shakhobiddinova

shakhlo.shakhobiddinova.95@mail.ru

+998900446687

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8016449>**Annotation:**

This article describes the essence of the tourism economy, the main factors in the development of tourism management, the types of tourism products and their distribution, the role of tourism in the development of the country's economy, the stages of development of management in the tourism industry, the methods of managing the tourism industry and its effectiveness.

Аннотация:

В данной статье рассмотрены сущность туристской экономики, основные факторы развития туристского менеджмента, виды туристского продукта и их распространение, роль туризма в развитии экономики страны, этапы развития туристского менеджмента. отрасли, методы управления туристической отраслью и ее эффективность.

Key words: management, tourism, infrastructure, tour operator, travel agencies, tourism industry, manager, excursion.

Ключевые слова: менеджмент, туризм, инфраструктура, туроператор, туристические агентства, индустрия туризма, менеджер, экскурсия.

Tourism is an economic segment, the development of which not only contributes to sustainable economic growth, but also ensures the socio-economic security of individual destinations, regions and, ultimately, the state.

In addition to the emergence of new types of tourist activities, in modern conditions, the attention of tourism enterprises should be focused on the person of the consumer from the goods and services they produce. The image of the tourist offer comes to the fore both at the level of relations with consumers and at the previous stages of creating a tourist product, for example, when determining its price. And in this respect, in the field of tourism, such directions as economy and management play the main role.

In the tourism industry, there are many enterprises and organizations that in one way or another should correspond to a single territorial management system, in which the goal is to ensure long-term competitiveness in the market. An important problem of regional management is at the same time an important distinguishing feature of tourism organization management.

The task of management in tourism is not only to determine the general trends and laws of its development, but also to find its specific features. With the help of management, a

development strategy for the entire region and for a separate tourist organization should be developed.

Often, an attempt is made to determine the level of tourism development in the region through the indicators of overnight stays. But such indicators do not say anything about the accumulation of values. Calculating value accumulation indicators requires significant research that cannot be carried out in full due to lack of time and financial resources.

Tourism greatly affects the economy, ecology, politics, which in turn affects tourism. A tourist area benefits from visitors. The income from their services is the main income and is more important than the income from permanent residents of the region. Profits from tourism flow into the local economic cycle with a new flow and have a multiplier effect: it "passes" through the local economy.

The higher the amount of money that stays in the region, the more services are sold directly on the spot, that is, the stronger the local production. The region can also benefit ecologically from tourism if allocations are used to maintain the landscape and order.

Often, at the initial stage of tourism development, various structures are built at its expense. At the same time, tourists create high road traffic, cleaning the area from household waste and use of local nature. Tourism as an object of management is manifested in the complexity of tourist services.

In recent years, the importance of cooperation between tourism enterprises has increased, which can be carried out at the horizontal or vertical level.

Horizontal cooperation is joint work. It is carried out by enterprises that have the same interests in the fields of accommodation, service, tourist mediation, health care, etc.

Vertical cooperation is a combination of enterprises and organizations that strive to own the market and reduce dependence on other institutions. In most cases, such organizations include state tourism organizations organized at the national, regional and local levels, which deal with the regulation of places of rest and accommodation for tourists. These organizations are exposed to various integration effects depending on the level of development of the economy of their country. These are also associations of enterprises in the field of travel and hotel accommodation (for example, air transport companies with hotel chains).

A distinctive feature of tourism is its zonality, that is, the dependence of the volume of tourist services on natural and climatic conditions. When solving the management problem in tourism, this phenomenon should be taken into account by the managers of tourism enterprises, because the change in demand can significantly worsen the conditions for the operation of the entire tourism industry.

The tourism system is based on two subsystems: tourism subject and tourism object. A tourist subject is a participant of a tourist event or a tourist who is looking for opportunities to satisfy his needs by receiving certain tourist services. These services are provided by the tourism facility.

Tourism object means everything that can become a travel destination for a tourism (tourist) subject. It can be a broad or narrowly specialized tourist region with all its tourist structures.

The tourism system exists in a public environment. The world surrounding the tourism system is represented by economy, ecology, technology, politics and social system. The listed systems of the public environment have a strong influence on tourism, although they are not the only ones.

Tourism's dependence on the external environment is an open system that can and should be managed using modern management methods and principles. It is important for management to identify the most important factors of external influence and to develop effective methods of responding to them.

The World Tourism Organization defines a tourist region as an area with a large network of specialized facilities and services necessary for the organization of recreation, education or recreation, sold by professionals in the field of providing services to tourists or groups of tourists. Thus, a tourist region is a competitive entity that must be managed as both a travel destination, a tourism product, and a strategic business unit.

As a competitive unit, the strategic goal of the entire region is to ensure long-term competitiveness. The interaction of industries (hotels, transport, trade), their markets, population and the surrounding world affects the competitiveness of the region. Markets place high demands on products and thus stimulate the work of networks, and on the contrary, competitive networks are interested in maintaining and increasing demanding customers in the industry. Sectors that benefit well from tourism form a specific sector.

A population that has a positive attitude towards tourism in its territory is a guarantee of hospitality and helps to implement innovative tourism projects. The attitude of the population to positive and negative externalities also affects the competitiveness of the region by state.

A tourist region as a competitive unit includes:

- socio-economic system;
- tourism policy;
- politics of the surrounding world;
- economic interests;
- state interests;
- population interests;
- resources;
- ecological system.

Organizational structures that are part of tourism management include public and private organizations at the international, national, regional and local levels. They are necessary for planning the development of tourism, coordinating the marketing of tourist products. State organizations at the regional level develop tourism support programs in their regions.

. Such programs serve to develop tourism infrastructure, crafts, resort facilities and social tourism. In addition, these organizations carry out marketing.

When analyzing the management problems of any tourist region, it should be taken into account that there are private tourist organizations as well as state-owned ones. Among them:

- associations of tourist intermediaries;
- hotel and restaurant-type tourist organizations.
- local tourism organizations.
- advertising organizations to attract foreign tourists to the country.

The analysis of small and large tourist destinations showed that in large areas, high demands are placed on high-level marketing by organizations, and functions such as leading image planning, proposal formation and coordination are not mentioned. This fact seems appropriate, since local organizations manage these functions in their activities.

From the point of view of the leadership of the regional organization, different requirements are placed on higher and lower organizations.

The following is required from the top tourism organization: formation of the image of a large area; implementation of marketing abroad (coordination of joint activities); representative of the local organization in important tourism markets.

The term "management" (from English "management") has not been literally translated into another language. In English-speaking countries, it is used very loosely and with different meanings, but the meaning is always related to the management of economic activity.

Management is management in the conditions of the market and market economy, which determines the following: orientation of the company to market demands and needs, specific consumer needs, and organization of production of the types of products that are required and can bring profit. ; constant striving to improve production efficiency, that is, achieving high results at low cost; economic independence, providing freedom of decision-making to persons responsible for the final results of the company; constantly adjusting goals and programs depending on market conditions; the final result of the firm's activity (product money) that is opened on the market during the exchange process; the need to use computer technologies for modern information base, optimal solutions, multidimensional calculations. A travel agency is a complex socio-technological system, which is influenced by many and diverse factors of the external and internal environment. Therefore, management is a science and an art, it is studied theoretically and only people who have this ability master it perfectly. Managers should learn from experience and modify subsequent practice accordingly, taking into account the conclusions of theory. This approach allows not only to constantly replenish scientific knowledge, but also to develop the personal qualities of managers, the ability to apply their knowledge in practical work.

The tasks and functions of management are carried out through the activities of managers.

A manager is a specialist who is professionally engaged in management activities in a certain area of the company's activity (in this case, excursion or methodical).

The uniqueness of the tasks to be solved implies the intellectual, creative nature of management work. Managers make human, financial and physical resources as efficient as possible. They contain information that helps in making decisions necessary for a specific work subject - management functions. So, managers' work tools are, first of all, tools for working with information. The result of their activity is evaluated by achieving the set goals.

The manager defines the tasks in each group of goals and decides what and how to do to achieve these goals. Delivers them to employees; organization of the production of excursions and excursion programs, their promotion, implementation and execution.

The manager analyzes the activities and decisions necessary to achieve the goals; groups processes and tasks into an organizational structure; selects people to manage these processes and solve tasks; determines the criteria of performance indicators (quality, quantity of work). The leader analyzes, evaluates and reports the results to management, subordinates and colleagues; supports motivation and communication. It makes a team of people responsible for specific areas of activity.

The uniqueness of excursion activity as a management object predetermines the nature of the work of managers and the demands placed on them. The manager's work is creative in nature, requires multifaceted knowledge and indicates a person's tendency to analytical activity.

In conclusion, it is worth saying that tourism is an industry that does not stop developing even today, and for the comprehensive growth and development of this industry, the state must be economically strong, and quality conditions must be created for tourists visiting from

different regions, and at the same time it is necessary to make the training of qualified personnel in this field, including in the management network, a priority.

References:

1. Makhmudova, A. (2018). Ensuring the competitiveness of scientific approaches to ecotourism on the example of Uzbekistan. South Asian Journal of Marketing & Management Research.
2. Makhmudova, A. P. (2017). Factors increasing the sustainability of agricultural products. In the innovative development of modern science: problems, laws, perspectives.
3. Nabiev, G. A. and Bakirova, O. (2022). Formation of entrepreneurial competences among schoolchildren.
4. Nabiev, G. A., & Bakirova, O. (2022). Development of entrepreneurial competences among students of general education.
5. Gulomkhasanov, E., Abdullayev, N., & Jorayev, S. (2021). Development of tourism through means of transportation.
6. Gulomkhasanov, E., Roziyev, B., Lazizova, M., & Ochildiyev, B. (2022). Tourism is a strategic branch of the country's economy
7. Baum, T., (1998), Human Resources in the European Hospitality and Tourism Industry. Butterworth Heinemann, Oxford.
8. Brewton, C., (1998), Human Resources Management. Hotel and Restaurant Administration Quarterly, 39(1), pp. 50-59.
9. Gayich, Tamara M A. Management of human resources and tourism 2009.

